

classified according to grain fertility percentage. Of the 40 varieties studied, 19 were classified as restorers, 12 as partial restorers, and 9 as maintainers (see table). □

Fertility restorers, partial restorers, and maintainers of cytoplasmic male sterile line V20A. Bihar, India.

Variety or line	Grain fertility (%)
<i>Restorer (> 7.5% fertility)</i>	
RAU4045-2A	89.6
IR19748-28	88.8
BAU120-9	88.5
IR58	88.5
IR19728-3-2-3-3	88.0
IR54	85.7
IR36	85.5
IR60	85.4
Amrose	84.4
BAU146-9-2	82.9
BAU151-51	82.7
IRAT-112	82.1
RAU4045-6	81.9
BAU147-22	81.9
BAU151-54	81.3
IR50	77.9
IR24	77.9
P-33	77.7
OR165-28-4	75.7
<i>Partial restorer (10- 7.5% fertility)</i>	
Pusa 2-21	65.3
RAU4045-3	60.0
IR8	53.3
Kiran	49.3
Changlei	45.8
Culture-1	27.4
RP1848-21-3-5	21.3
Ratna	20.2
BAU151-56	17.2
Badshah Pasand	15.0
Saket-4	10.1
BAU122-2	10.1
<i>Maintainer (<10% fertility)</i>	
Bala	8.3
CR404-48	6.8
CH1039	6.5
IET7918	6.2
Annapurna	6.1
CH988	4.8
ADT30	4.2
CR407-19	3.8
Cauvery	3.2
CD (P=0.05)	6.66
CV = 9.00%	

Isozyme markers to monitor seed purity in indica hybrid rice

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Simple genetic markers are needed to assess the efficiency of systems for

Table 1. Discriminative power of isozyme markers among indica rices: probability (P) that 2 randomly chosen varieties differ for each individual marker and for a certain number of markers. IRRI, 1985.

Object of comparison	P
<i>Individual marker^a</i>	
<i>Amp-1</i> (2)	0.13
Block (<i>Amp-3</i> , <i>Est-2</i>) ^b (3)	0.61
<i>Pgi-2</i> (3)	0.50
<i>Pgi-1</i> (4)	0.13
<i>Sdh-1</i> (6)	0.52
<i>Pox-2</i> ^c (6)	0.50
<i>Acp-1</i> (6)	0.04
<i>Est-9</i> (7)	0.45
<i>Amp-2</i> (8)	0.02
<i>Adh-1</i> (11)	0.02
<i>Pgd-1</i> (11)	0.55
<i>Est-1</i> ^c (?)	0.06
<i>Acp-4</i> (?)	0.39
<i>Mal-1</i> (?)	0.04
<i>Number of markers</i>	
0	0.00
1	0.03
2	0.11
3	0.21
4	0.26
5	0.21
6	0.11
7	0.04
8	0.01
9	0.00
>9	

^aChromosome number in parentheses. ^bBlock of 2 tightly linked loci, showing strong linkage disequilibrium. ^cInvolving one null allele (recessive) in significant frequency.

Table 2. Variation at 10 loci among 6 CMS, 4 B, and 8 R lines of the WA cyto sterility system. IRRI, 1987.

Line	Plants analyzed (no.)	Most frequent allelic constitution at 10 loci ^a										Frequency (%) of other types
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10*	
<i>A lines</i>												
Zhen Shan 97A	156	1	2*	2*	1	1	2	1*	1	2*	2*	32.1
V20A	88	1	1*	2*	1	1	2	1*	1	2*	2*	31.8
IR46830A	801	2*	1	1	1	1	2	2	1	1	1	5.0
IR54752A	605	1	1*	1*	1	1	2	2*	1	1*	1	0.5
IR54753A	167	1	1*	1	1	1	2	2*	1	1*	1	0.6
IR54754A	88	1	1	1	1	1	2	2*	1	1*	1	1.1
<i>B lines</i>												
Zhen Shan 97	114	1	2	2	1	1	2	1	1	2	2	0
V20A	102	1	1*	2*	1	1	2	1*	1*	2*	2*	8.8
IR46830	144	1	2	1*	1	1	2	2	1	1	1	2.8
IR54752	104	1	1*	1	1	1	2*	2*	1	1*	1	2.9
<i>R lines</i>												
Milyang 46	147	1	1	4*	1	1	2	2*	1	1*	2	0.7
Milyang 54	110	1	2	1	1	1	2	1*	0	2*	1	15.5
IR9761-19-1	104	1	1*	1	1	1	2	1*	1	2*	1	6.7
IR13292-5-3	213	1	2	1	1	1	2	2*	0	1*	2*	8.5
IR14753-120-3	154	1	2*	1*	1	1	2	1*	0	2*	1	9.7
IR19392-211-1	117	1	2*	1	1	1	2	1*	1	2*	1	11.1
IR20933-68-21-1-2	110	1	2	1*	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	1.8
IR54R	131	1	2*	1*	1	1	2	1	0*	2	1	5.3

^a1 = *Pgi-1*, 2 = *Pgi-2*, 3 = *Sdh-1*, 4 = *Adh-1*, 5 = *Amp-1*, 6 = *Amp-2*, 7 = *Amp-3*, 8 = *Est-1*, 9 = *Est-2*, 10 = *Est-9*, 1 = locus where several alleles have been found within the line.

hybrid seed production by differentiating the seeds resulting from the expected combination from those produced by selfing and those produced by foreign pollen.

We investigated polymorphism of genes coding for isozymes among the indica rices to determine their potential to address this matter. The survey of 900 traditional varieties identified 14 polymorphic genes expressed in young shoots, among which 9 are highly polymorphic. Thus, isozymes provide a very powerful means of discrimination among indica rices (Table 1).

We used some of these enzymes to characterize six cytoplasmic male sterile (CMS), four maintainer (B), and eight restorer (R) lines for the wild aborted (WA) cyto sterility system (Table 2). Each line presents a dominant allelic combination, with minor combinations observed in variable frequencies. The dominant combination in any CMS line is different from that in any R line. Thus, after preliminary purification, these genes will be useful in determining hybrid seed purity. □